

Traditional Learning Versus E- Learning in the Academia : A Comparative Study of the Prospects and Problematics of Education in the Digital World.

Dr. Noheir Taha Hassan Mohamed

Assistant Professor at the Department of Basic Sciences Adham University College, Umm AlQura University

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ABSTRACT

In previous studies, the online learning vs traditional learning implications have formerly been discussed for many years in higher education levels. The theme of this research work had emerged as an outcome of the remarkable ongoing technological growth, as well as the enduring digital trends. Consequently, the market is currently altering the traditional teaching strategies and classical learning practices. In fact, the outdated educational process is changing and a new one its emerging. More learning opportunities are introduced and recommended because of the progressions in the teaching and learning processes, which will enhance, and advance education. Moreover, this study will examine the benefits and drawbacks of traditional learning and E-learning. On one hand, it will focus on traditional learning styles, which generally require a physical space, including a classroom, where schools and instructors can interact. On the other hand, it will discuss E-learning styles, which mainly include an e-space with a server and a web browsing interface.

1. Introduction

In education, modern information technology offers promises but also causes some problematics. It is an undeniable fact that the educational sector is considered among the major sectors which has immensely benefited from information technology. Nevertheless, few nations which are successful in education have access to technological advancements in the education field. Therefore, many countries around the world are striving to manage the difficulties and cope with the challenges of the global integration and adoption of modern technology into the educational process by improving their information skills and expertise. As regards the learning and teaching process in the academia, it is worthy of mentioning that modern technology and e-learning have become crucially essential factors that require more attention. In this sense, within the field of higher education, the adoption of e-learning has become an indispensable issue for researchers who are concerned with the education (Garaika & Margahana, 2020). Distant learners can access educational programs through e-learning. However, e-learning is a platform for online learning that can develop in a formal setting and utilizes various multimedia technologies. Such modern technological expertise involves both hardware and software skills as well as the electronic support of this system both online and offline. Besides, in an attempt to deliver a computer-enhanced learning, the personal computer is usually applied and implemented in relation to internet learning (Samsuri, Nadzri, & Rom, 2014). In fact, education and communication are conducted through various technologies to deliver tutorials, online, lectures, and learning support systems (Kattoua, Al-Lozi, & Alrowwad, 2016). Undoubtedly, E-learning is an influential technology for enhancing

the learning process by creating modern classroom environments whose major features are competence, excellence, participation, and interaction, where the students are intentionally engaged for completing the task during online tutorials.

Recent studies indicated that university students outperformed while taking their e-learning courses more than they did when they were enrolled into traditional courses. At Carnegie Mellon University, the students' exam results have shown great improvement, particularly in the implementation of e-learning technique. In the learning process, incorporating technology does not guarantee that students would stay motivated. This is because a virtual gap has been created by the online instructions during the student-teacher computer-generated communication, so much so that the educational process has eventually become less personal. Even though, turning the classroom into an online environment will be the top priority for modern teachers. In this respect, an intricate issue for consideration is how to instruct teachers to motivate their students in an online environment (Abou El-Seoud et al., 2014).

In UAE, a rapid change is being experienced in higher education, including a huge technological transformation considering the rapid network accessibility. Knowledge is being created and executed at a higher education setting with creative methods to acquire the insights and share the changes in technology at an increased rate. Online classes or courses are being provided by educational institutions using the course delivery of face-to-face and online elements. Educational institutions offer different courses by using technology or web-based facilities whereby assignments, course contents, and assessments are uploaded and corrected. This means that it becomes significantly important to acknowledge the pros and cons of the modern educational process as observed through the learner and acting further for online learning's successful integration. As a matter of fact, eLearning is experiencing a revolutionary stage because of the technological advancement. The new gadgets, innovative tools, and equipment have made the dreams of eLearning come true. Hence, this study aims at the identification of the advanced technological trends that had an influential impact on the e-learning process and had offered new ways to deliver content.

To achieve a genuine study of the e-learning prominent effect on academic performance, a thorough interpretation of the concept of e-learning is a demanding requirement. To define e-learning, different terminologies had been implemented. For example, a major requirement is the identification of the type of learning system which is electronically utilized to access the curriculum outside the face-to-face classrooms. A recent research paper about e-learning, provided a brief discussion of the learning and teaching methods that partially signify the educational model used (Salloum, Alhamad, Al-Emran, Monem, & Shaalan, 2019). On the basis of the electronic devices and media that are implemented for the enhancement of communication, and development of training and availability, this media channel provides help in accepting the novel methods of establishing such learning strategies (Alghizzawi et al., 2019). In simple terms, the courses of e-learning that are delivered specifically by the internet are far from the face-to-face class by virtue of its rapidly advancing learning schemes. By that means, e-learning does not only foster the use of network technologies to facilitate and create unlimited virtual learning platforms anywhere and anytime. In fact, it encourages individual learners to empower and enforce their skills so that the tutor, trainer, or teacher will no longer act as a gatekeeper of knowledge. On the contrary, the teacher's role as a facilitator of knowledge has always been viewed (Salloum et al., 2019). This research paper has also briefly stated that E-learning is identified as a concept that unifies the

disciplines of online education, web-based training, and technologically supported instruction. (Alabi, 2021)

Significance of the study

This research work is assumably both fundamental and influential in this field of study. For instance, the results of the study will assist readers to overview the varied attitudes, aspects of eLearning. In addition to this, it is meant to enhance the academic performance by providing the crucially essential information to carry the research further in similar areas. The study also provides the guidelines and knowledge for planners, policymakers, and students as well as researchers.

E-learning Model

The world-wide extensive prevalence of mobile devices like tablets, smartphones as well as laptops, which are also considered to be synonymous with social media 2.0, has opened new opportunities in the context of education whether teaching or learning. It has been assumed that the impact of globalization continues to influence the expansion and progression of both general knowledge and technology that requires technical skills, critical thinking, and creativity. Furthermore, it is also seen as an intricate aspect of the acceleration of development and civilization advancement (Cartner & Hallas, 2017). In the world of education, the increasing progress of information and communication technology triggers a transitional tendency from face-to-face conventional learning to contemporary learning. Such educational shift is based on online learning that can easily be accessed by utilizing technological media, such as hardware and software devices and worldwide internet systems which are accessed without limits of space or time. Computer-assisted learning or eLearning is usually used by most learners to support them in their studies through communication models. In this sense, computers are considered among the indispensable devices in the prosperity of education including both teaching and learning (Muali et al., 2018). It is true that, unlike traditional pedagogy, educators must rethink their approaches to teaching to realize the e-learning potential as an effective teaching strategy. It has been claimed that online learning is considered to be a teaching and learning process that heavily utilizes information technology as an effective means in studying skills (Muali et al., 2018). In fact, it is true that with the inauguration of eLearning in society, learners became more empowered self-assisted students because the educational process is no longer a teacher-centered process but has switched to become student-centered, student-oriented procedure. The implementation of cloud platforms and social media has launched innovative solutions for collaborative teaching and learning (Vickers, Field, & Melakoski, 2015).

The theory of online collaborative learning (OCL) mainly concentrates on educational applications that facilitate the creation and realization of unique ideas. Furthermore, the theory of OCL consists of three intellectual phases: generating ideas, organizing ideas and intellectual convergence (Mnkandla & Minnaar, 2017). Furthermore, between the learning media learners have an important disconnect that optimally works for millennials and ordinary media experience. Moreover, learners believe that for the students this effort can provide optimal results before looking at the teaching content details. This is because it is considered very important to compare and contrast individuals involved and related to the education process (Arnold, 2016). The combination of e-learning and traditional forms of learning is also known as hybrid learning. However, whereas hybrid learning evaluates training activities, the traditional forms of training like the classroom learning are combined with eLearning supplements.

Comparing traditional learning and E-learning

It was deeply argued that traditional learning is an efficient way for maintaining the learning process. Other models are known to be inferior and less efficient. It is also true that as such there are no results or findings to support this argument. Thus, this study attempts to show that the models of technology supported education are usually as good as the traditional learning. As a matter of fact, many components are included in E-learning that are like traditional learning among which are: ideas of presentation, group discussion, students conveying information. Some other advantages are involved in e-learning but not found in traditional learning, such as the time for processing the information, the increased mode of communication among the learners themselves, the capacity to hold an open discussion where each learner has more of an equal status than in a face-to-face discussion, access to information and the capacity to hold discussions, the ability to discuss responses whenever it is convenient, and a higher level of learner motivation and involvement in the process.

Comparison between traditional learning and E-learning

	E-learning	Traditional Learning
Learning Process	Individual student or students' group takes place in the learning process	With the whole class participating, the learning is being conducted; there is no individual study or group
Lesson Structure	The lessons' structure is affected by the group dynamics.	The lessons' structure and time's division are usually dictated by the teachers.
Motivation	The motivations of student are very high because of their involvement in contemporary technology that matches their modern way of thinking.	The motivation of student is very low, and the subject matter is distant from them.
Classroom Discussions	Students participate and share in discussions.	As compared to students, teachers usually do all the talking.
Emphasis in the learning process	Students focus on the HOW of learning less than the WHAT; this research work includes learning which combines collecting information from the banks of web data as well as to the real world where the learning is better connected, and the subject matter from different formats includes material.	The students focus on learning the WHAT not the HOW; the teachers and students are finishing the needed quota subject matter. Nevertheless, students in inquiry-based education are not involved in solving the problems.
Teachers Role	The teacher instructs students to obtain knowledge.	The teacher is the authority.
Location of learning	learning take place anywhere with no fixed location.	Learning takes place within the school and classroom.
Subject Matter	By analyzing the subject matter students usually participate; studying is based on different information resources, which include banks of web data and net expert located with the help of students.	The lesson is usually conducted by the teacher according to a fixed curriculum and study program.

E-Learning Advantages and Disadvantages

Advantages

Undoubtedly, e-learning is an optimal choice for the education as it has various benefits more specifically for the institutions of higher education. For example, academic personnel scarcities are compensated by e-learning which includes instructors or coaches, staff as well as laboratory technicians. In addition, e-learning increases the competency and efficiency of knowledge by the suitable accessibility to mass of information (Arkorful & Abaidoo, 2015). It is an undeniable fact that achieving higher degrees without leaving the current job is only ensured by distance education which has become the most appropriate choice (Hosseindoost, Khan, & Majedi, 2022). Wherever the learner is around the world, distance learning facilitates participation. Still, the course content can be easily accessed, particularly if it is offered by an international institution (Hosseindoost et al., 2022).

Disadvantages

E-learning's most common weakness is the lack of high personal interaction between the educators, colleagues, and learners. In traditional learning the process of face to face learning is very comfortable and easier as compared to e-learning (Al Rawashdeh, Mohammed, Al Arab, Alara, & Al-Rawashdeh, 2021). In traditional education, when a student is required to communicate about lectures with educators, it is generally to interact before or after the class with teacher. On the contrary, it was argued that in distance learning, learners usually face more challenges or difficulties while interacting with their instructors. For example, emails could be sent by them; they might not receive a response as in physical learning. This means that the approach of e-learning process can be less efficient as compared to the methods of traditional learning (Hutt, 2017). For any assignment the missing and dropping out deadlines' possibility is very high because of the absence of physical interaction. Furthermore, if learners are willing to complete their course of distance education, then they need to stay focused and motivated. Otherwise, for improving the socialization ability, e-learning is inappropriate for communication skills to guide and instruct learners. In the educational process, the presence of supervisors restricts the instructor's role (Arkorful & Abaidoo, 2015). In addition to this, learners do not have the opportunity to practice and study their lessons orally. The learners also have higher knowledge of the educational strategies. This is because to present their knowledge socially they should be technologically skillful as in institutionalized learning, where the learners communicate and interact on a personal level with all the people. On the contrary, learners usually study alone in distance learning and therefore they may miss the social interaction and feel solitary in traditional courses. In the training process the lack of physical communication can create various challenges and difficulties like depression and isolation (Huggett, 2014). It was briefly argued that it is very challenging to control or manage the activities due to monitored proxies in e-learning of examinations and assessments. Therein, e-learning can also become a major cause of plagiarism. The other disadvantage of e-learning is that this type of education cannot be used effectively through all disciplines. For instance, in the scientific specialties that require the skillful and functional usage of hands, there is a possibility of more difficulties or challenges through e-learning. It was deeply determined in the research that e-learning is more appropriate in humanities rather than in technicalities as social sciences, like medicine and engineering, where practical skills must have developed. E-learning in congestion can also overuse some of websites. For example, to stare at screens digitally more time is required (Hosseindoost, Khan, and Majedi 2022). Students who enroll in a distance education program should finance various kinds of equipment, like the webcam, computer, and stable internet connection. Generally, it has been shown that 20-49% less time and effort is spent on traditional

classroom as compared to online courses (Mishra, Gupta, & Shree, 2020). Furthermore, it is believed that the technical issues of e-learning are the bigger challenge. The complex quality of technology limits online education to learners who are familiar with technology and computer skills as well. In case of hardware and software failure, the session of the class is interrupted due to absence of physical communication between the instructors and learners, which easily disrupts the learning process. In e-learning, reliance on technology is the most crucial disadvantage (He, Zha, & Li, 2013). In addition to this, a high possibility risk to the labor market's private companies and government employers who might not approve of hiring employees beholding a distance education degrees because organizations prefer traditional college to e-learning of certification. At some point they still believe that traditional learning would meet standard form of education (Hosseindoost et al., 2022). Moreover, other e- disadvantage of e-learning involved the absence of physical activity, increased eye exhaustion, as well as concentration and lack of personal discipline.

E-learning Environment

The environment of new learning based on electronic network has enabled the students and learners to aid individually in a proper manner and to have learning schedules that are more comfortable for them and separate from other learners. The usage of interactive structures distinguished e-learning in academia, it also has made the process of learning more involved, pleasurable and engaging. In the environment of classroom, the explanations and course materials distribution are shared in the way of using e-learning between the method of conventional learning and e-learning system. In Saudi Arabia, the understanding and effectiveness of e-learning have discovered models of e-learning usage in education, mixed e-learning and namely supplement. The evolution and expansion of e-learning has introduced different changes in the higher education institution, the online course's ability in an increasingly growing sector of cyber education is also improvised. As a tool, e-learning can have a detrimental effect when it comes to improving the communication skills of learners. However, e-learning is a tool that enables the learners to experience distance, reflection and lack of relationship as well. Moreover, compared with the conventional method of e-learning the method of e-learning can be less successful. The role of socialization of agencies can also be deteriorated by E-learning and the role of teachers like the supervisors of educational process. Through plagiarism and piracy e-learning can also be fooled with ease copy and paste and poor search skills.

Higher Education

Education has long been seen as a significant resource and a fundamental factor in any country's prosperity. In fact, planning, designing, and launching upgraded modern technologically modified educational programs aim at eliminating poverty, improving local economies, or increasing population's health. E-learning can also help to compensate for academic staff scarcity which includes instructors or teachers and laboratory technicians as well. E-learning enables self-monitoring. For instance, the asynchronous approach enables each student to study according to their own learning style, level, and pace. It is an undeniable fact that there have been various initiatives of open learning for decades. Thus, MOOC's popularity, growth and availability will have a wider impact on higher education in public (Kannadhasan, Shanmuganantham, Nagarajan, & Deepa, 2020). The world's workforce is also experiencing a significant transformation to cope and compete with the rapid mobility and maturity of the career market. This is observed in the inauguration of the growing workforce and the innovation of knowledge-based and technology-centered or computer-adjusted jobs. The rapid increase in the work teams of multidisciplinary work teams engaged in problem solving and creativity represents a high demand for continuous

workplace in the field of education. It is worthy of noting that the sustainability of higher education is of great importance for the achievement of national prosperity which is achieved through the contributions of the developments in higher education, and the advanced and enhanced skills and qualities of its people and their competence in the world market. Such initiatives attain international arena and collaborate in intercontinental organizations, involving its different faculty members and students as well.

Apart from the continuing and growing demand for collaborations and international ties, different difficulties and diverse challenges persistently confront participants in the system of higher education. In the time being, technology is rapidly becoming significant to the cycle of higher education whether teaching or learning. Furthermore, it allows the broad accessibility to education and training. Likewise, the huge technological development paves the way for the variability in the individual learning styles, online interaction, community learning and gaming and real time employer projects to formulate the educations as per requirements. As a matter of fact, open distance learning and e-learning have gained the momentum as worldwide new dynamic and flexible ways to acquire professional experience and academic knowledge in a global environment. Therefore, and according to the above discussion, both European and American literature is briefly addressing the MOOCs from an academic status and is considering the advantages and disadvantages of MOOCs universities, issues of distribution and MOOC development to forecast the effect of MOOC on university models and analyze its patterns.

Why Blended Learning?

The computer mediated scholastic system of blended learning (BL) functions as an integrative combination of physically instructive learning (Hrastinski, 2019). This is demonstrated in its conceptual definition that such instructive education is rather a combination and a blend of two different learning models, namely, the system of distributed learning and traditional face to face learning systems. However, it also evaluates the major key factors of technologies which are computer based and in blended learning. It is true that there are several other reasons that a trainer, learner, or instructor might pick blended learning and seek it as an ideal learning option. In recent research that studied this issue, six different reasons were identified for choosing to implement or design a system of blended learning. Among such factors are access to knowledge, pedagogical richness, ease of revision, social interaction, personal agency, and cost effectiveness (Tupe, 2018). Furthermore, (BL) has become utterly significant and is closely related to E-learning and distance learning. Regardless to the alluring benefits such as flexibility, accessibility as well as cost savings of e-learning, it is worthy of noting that in such eLearning process the physical interaction is missing. Uploading the learning material and resources online does not mean or ensure that the learning process will occur automatically. To create and develop good courses of e-learning the learning skills and culture, it is considered to be a big challenge. Many educational organizations, educators and learners shifted to the traditional mode after experiencing suffering from the exhausting problematics of e-learning (Azlan et al., 2020).

Students Perception of Learning

The education has undergone an enormous transformation after the outbreak of coronavirus pandemic. The learning process has shifted from face-to-face classes to online virtual meetings. Consequently, over the course of time mixing or combing two forms of learning became the trend which is also related to blended learning. On the outbreak of the Covid19, all the lectures were conducted online to restrain the physical contact among the students and the teachers and control

the spread of the virus. It is worthy of noting that in traditional education, learning is a process dependent on delivering lectures, whereas on face to face learning, students are spontaneously involved in verbal communication and permanently in a physical environment (Tang & Chaw, 2013). Physical learning or attending classes or lectures is considered a classical form of teacher-centered learning where the students' involvement is weak (Nasution, Surbakti, Zakaria, Wahyuningsih, & Daulay, 2021). The IAIN Takengon in Indonesia, physical learning involves delivering presentations and discussions. However, modern technological teaching strategies and different kinds of learning methods are incorporated in the physical learning classes which are carried out and conducted in the face-to-face classroom. The total number of meetings in an ordinary semester is 16 which includes both final and midterm exams.

Furthermore, hybrid learning is known to be blended learning, that uses several different learning approaches. This refers to the combination between face to face and online learning with the accessibility of structured learning to faculty members (Singh, Steele, & Singh, 2021). Such a new type of learning implements a variety of training media whose combination is meant to create a guidance program exclusively optimal for a particular audience. Herein the term "mixed" shows that training can be led by instructors who teach both physically and by employing other complementary electronic formats. The programs of mixed learning use different forms of e-learning, and can also be complemented by other different instructors that participate in training using various formats directly (Yuliyana, Rochmiyati, & Maulina, 2021). The students' learning experience is usually a positive one and results in blending different forms of physical and virtual learning in higher student achievement (Fisher, Perényi, & Birdthistle, 2021). In IAIN Takengon the blended learning is done usually by combing traditional learning and online learning. Other than that, online learning is implemented through diverse platforms like the google classroom, e-learning, and WhatsApp. Using the e-learning Moodle has been developed in IAIN Takengon. However, it is true that Moodle of computer-assisted learning is considered authentic and has a reliability of bigger level and it is usually used in the university (Daulay, Zakaria, Surbakti, Nasution, & Wahyuningsih, 2021). For the internet use, online learning is all about the accessibility of learning material, to communicate with lecturers, deliver or receive study content and other studying facilities; it is also for obtaining help in the learning process through gathering more knowledge to build a robust personal meaning and mature through the learning experience (Daulay et al., 2021). With telecommunication, the online media is more concerned with the functional importance of technology, not simply as a product, but, rather with the networks of communication which is computer-based (Nasution et al., 2021). However, in Takengon IAIN one semester was conducted as an offline lecture because of the bigger challenges of the media including internet problems of weak connections and other similar critical issues that problematize the process of eLearning and blended learning.

As a matter of fact, the learning achievement of student perception provided additional information, and allowed the educators to acknowledge the student's point of view about the learning goals that are properly met and the objectives of the learning outcomes are realized (Bhardwaj & Goundar, 2018). The student's perception's identification is the most significant part of analyzing the methods used by the teachers. The identification is just to distinguish the needs of students for their learning activities and to acquire learning objectives (Paterson, 2017). Currently, it is the optimal time to conduct a research on the learning outcomes from the student's perspective, where there are varied chances to judge blended learning, face to face learning or online learning, and, thus, to provide researchers in this field with enriching findings and inspiring

recommendations to broaden the global overview on the future of the educational process and its improvement and enhancement.

Conclusion

Universities are now more technologically equipped to provide online classes and to create more opportunities for blended learning or remote learning. Additionally, this study was designed to investigate how different levels of students perceived online learning and face-to-face learning. Although, throughout this argument there is a powerful contest based on the claim that online learning results in less social engagement, a loss of interaction, and synchronization in communication, yet the advantages outweigh the disadvantages. In the process of carrying out this research study, it rather seemed that as such there it does not matter these kinds of treatments in learning, as they all have their pros and cons. That is to say that the methodology for a particular student is supposed to be suitable whereas another is not. However, some activities that are related to more efficient learning are included: e-learning is required to provide once or twice meeting per semester whereas face-to-face learning is needed to make up for the limited size of classes offered by e-learning facilities like the blog, E-store, and chat room. In this study, the researcher highly suggests that mixed and blended learning which is a combination of e-learning and face to face learning (traditionally) would be an improvement in the student's academic achievement. Apart from that the size of small class in traditional or face to face learning is considered to be another element of its success.

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